

FREEDOM OF CONSCIENCE AND SUSTAINABLE PEACE: THE INTEGRATION OF DEATH ANXIETY INTO THE NARRATIVE OF HOPE

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ABSTRACT: *Freedom of Conscience and Sustainable Peace: The Integration of Death Anxiety into the Narrative of Hope.*

This article argues that freedom of conscience is the foundation of human dignity and the premise of lasting peace, as it transforms the fear of death from an instrument of manipulation into a resource of meaning and civic responsibility. The integration of psychology, existential philosophy, and theology shows that the assumption of finitude is the condition of authenticity, and martyrdom becomes the supreme expression of this freedom: a public pedagogy of dignity and a reference point for human rights. Biographical narrative integrates death anxiety into a redemptive framework, with formative effects for civic and spiritual education. The conclusion affirms that only the person free in conscience can build peace, and the memory of martyrs remains a transgenerational model.

Keywords: *freedom of conscience; fear of death; existentialism; Terror Management Theory (TMT); theology; human dignity; human rights; narrative education; martyrdom; sustainable peace.*

1. Introduction

Freedom of conscience represents the foundation of human dignity and the central point from which human rights, authentic education, and the possibility of lasting peace are born.¹ It is not only a legal right, but above all an inner reality, an anchor of being in truth and meaning, which is tested in moments of existential crisis. Confrontation with death constitutes one of these fundamental trials, since the fear of death has been constantly described by theologians, psychologists, and philosophers as the most universal and most difficult human anxiety to manage.²

Henri Nouwen observed that our society is “full of fears,” the most profound of which is the fear of death, a fear that “takes away our freedom and gives society the power to manipulate us through threats and promises”³. This observation shows how fear can be transformed into a political and social instrument, while freedom of conscience becomes the essential antidote against collective manipulation, thereby grounding human rights and peaceful coexistence.

In the same line, Irvin Yalom underlines that “anxiety about nothing” is, in essence, anxiety about death, which quickly attaches itself to tangible objects.⁴ Ernest Becker argues that “human activity is largely driven by unconscious efforts to deny and transcend death,” formulating this idea within a cultural framework: the denial of death is the driving force of civilization, and religious, political, and educational institutions have the role of creating symbols that mitigate the fundamental fear of disappearance.⁵ Therefore, freedom of conscience is what allows the in-

1 Uniunea Europeană, *Carta Drepturilor Fundamentale a Uniunii Europene*, art. 10, „Libertatea de gândire, de conștiință și de religie,” accesat 18 septembrie 2025, <https://fra.europa.eu/ro/eu-charter/article/10-libertatea-de-gandire-de-constiinta-si-de-religie>.

2 Raoul Dederen, *Handbook of Seventh-Day Adventist Theology*, ed. electronică, vol. 12, Commentary Reference Series (Hagerstown, MD: Review and Herald Publishing Association, 2001), 330. Irvin D. Yalom, *Psihoterapia existențială*, trad. Bogdan Boghițoi (București: Editura Trei, 2010), 45–47. Costica Brădățan, “Philosophy as an Art of Dying,” *Opinionator*, June 12, 2011, <https://archive.nytimes.com/opinionator.blogs.nytimes.com/2011/06/12/philosophy-as-an-art-of-dying/>.

3 Henri J. M. Nouwen, *Our Greatest Gift: A Meditation on Dying and Caring* (San Francisco: HarperSanFrancisco, 1995), 17.

4 Irvin D. Yalom, *Staring at the Sun: Overcoming the Terror of Death* (San Francisco: Jossey-Bass, 2008), 22.

5 Sheldon Solomon, Jeff Greenberg, and Tom Pyszczynski, *The Worm at the Core* (Random House, 2015), 6.

dividual not to remain a prisoner of these mechanisms, but to transform them into a framework of dignity and authentic education.

From a theological perspective, Robert S. Folkenberg pointed out that many Christians live lives dominated by fear, uncertain of their salvation, and unable to enjoy the peace promised in Christ.⁶

Thus, from the very introduction, it becomes evident that freedom of conscience is not only an abstract concept, but a practical foundation for human rights, for an education that cultivates courage, and for lasting peace that cannot be built on fear. This tension between faith and fear reveals how central freedom of conscience is for spiritual life: only a liberated conscience can transform the fear of death into a living hope.

Existentialist philosophy has deepened this theme. Kierkegaard described existential anxiety as the “dizziness of freedom”⁷, the awareness that we are finite and yet called to radical choices. Heidegger spoke of man as a “being-toward-death”⁸, for whom authenticity begins when he assumes his own finitude. Sartre emphasized the absolute responsibility of human freedom⁹, while Viktor Frankl, through logotherapy, showed that the meaning of life is the fundamental antidote to death anxiety¹⁰.

This line of reflection is also taken up by Costică Brădățan, who argues that voluntarily assumed death in the name of an idea or belief is not an act of despair, but the supreme expression of freedom of conscience. The martyr demonstrates that there are values higher than biological survival, and his sacrifice becomes an educational, communal, and cultural act, with echoes in the building of authentic peace.¹¹

Freedom of conscience thus takes shape as an interdisciplinary space in which theology brings eschatological hope and frames the fear of death

6 Robert S. Folkenberg, *Called in Christ* (Nampa, Idaho: Pacific Press® Publishing Association, 2013), 49.

7 Søren Kierkegaard, *The Concept of Anxiety: A Simple Psychologically Orienting Deliberation on the Dogmatic Issue of Hereditary Sin* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1980), 61.

8 Martin Heidegger, *Ființă și timp*, trad. Gabriel Liiceanu și Cătălin Cioabă (București: Humanitas, 2003), 615.

9 Paul Vincent Spade, *Jean-Paul Sartre's Being and Nothingness: Class Lecture Notes, Spring 2010* (Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License), 101, 117.

10 Viktor E. Frankl, *Man's Search for Meaning: An Introduction to Logotherapy* (Boston: Beacon Press, 1992), 85.

11 Costică Brădățan, *Dying for Ideas: The Dangerous Lives of the Philosophers* (London: Bloomsbury UK, 2015), 7.

within the horizon of resurrection¹², psychology explains the mechanisms of managing existential anxiety through narrative and identity reconstruction¹³, and philosophy directs reflection toward authenticity in the face of finitude, highlighting the role of confronting death in the constitution of meaning¹⁴. This convergence shows that freedom of conscience is not only a legal right, but also a spiritual and cultural resource that sustains human dignity and cultivates the possibility of lasting peace.¹⁵

Therefore, the theme of this article is the exploration of freedom of conscience in relation to the fear of death and martyrdom, in dialogue with philosophical reflections, Christian theological foundations, and psychological perspectives on existential anxiety. Such an approach reveals how death, although inevitable, can become not a defeat, but a space of victory for inner freedom and the affirmation of human dignity.¹⁶ Consequently, I proceed from the psychological foundations of the fear of death to the ways in which these are integrated spiritually and existentially, in order to show how freedom of conscience transforms fundamental anxiety into a resource of dignity, education, and peace.

2. Fear of Death and Inner Freedom

The fear of death has been called “the most fundamental fear of human beings”¹⁷, an anxiety that permeates all dimensions of existence. It is not

12 Narcisa Ispas, “Terror Management Theory and Fear of Death,” *Scientia Morali-tas Conference Proceedings*, February 20–21, 2025: 104–112, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15075876>.

13 Narcisa Ispas, “Christian Narrative Therapy: Reconstructing Identity and Spiritual Healing Through Story,” *RAIS Journal for Social Sciences* 9, no. 1 (2025): 119–137, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15428078>.

14 Narcisa Ispas, “Existential Perspectives on the Fear of Death,” *RAIS Conference Proceedings*, April 17–18, 2025: 183–190, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15474925>.

15 United Nations, *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*, art. 18 (1948), <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>;

Uniunea Europeană, *Carta Drepturilor Fundamentale a Uniunii Europene*, art. 10, accesat 18 septembrie 2025, <https://fra.europa.eu/ro/eu-charter/article/10-libertatea-de-gandire-de-constiinta-si-de-religie>;

16 Ispas, “Existential Perspectives on the Fear of Death”.

17 Raoul Dederen, *Handbook of Seventh-Day Adventist Theology*, ed. electronică, vol. 12, Commentary Reference Series (Hagerstown, MD: Review and Herald Publishing Association, 2001), 330.

reducible to a mere biological instinct of self-preservation but constitutes a psychological and spiritual core that shapes values, behaviors, and social institutions.¹⁸ Therefore, the way each era and community manages this fear becomes directly linked to freedom of conscience and to the construction of a free society—or, conversely, an oppressive one.

Ernest Becker shows that human heroism is nothing more than a reflex of the terror of death, which is why people have transformed courage into the highest cultural value. At the same time, religious cults and spiritual traditions have been built upon the promise of resurrection and upon rituals of symbolic defeat of death. Paradoxically, although the fear of death remains ever-present in our biological structure, in daily life it is often repressed, leading us to behave as if we were immortal.¹⁹ In this context, freedom of conscience proves to be the space where repression of fear is replaced by the conscious assumption of dignity and meaning, thereby opening the way for an education in courage and for the cultivation of a culture of peace.

2.1. Psychological Paradigms

Irvin Yalom emphasizes that every human being carries within themselves a “taste of death,” visible in everyday experiences such as sleep or anesthesia.²⁰ In his view, existential anxiety cannot be eliminated, but it can be confronted and transformed.²¹ Terror Management Theory (Greenberg, Pyszczynski & Solomon, 1986) conceptualized this intuition, showing that the mere awareness of the inevitability of death activates existential defense mechanisms—such as the pursuit of self-esteem, belonging to a community, and cultural validation—meant to protect the individual from psychological paralysis.²²

Empirical studies confirm that the fear of death stimulates both prosocial behaviors (compassion, solidarity) and negative reactions (aggressiveness, prejudice, intolerance). This ambivalence of existential anxiety shows that the fear of death can be either a source of closure and

18 Ispas, “Terror Management Theory and Fear of Death”.

19 Ernest Becker, *The Denial of Death* (New York: Free Press, 1973), 11–12, 17.

20 Yalom, *Staring at the Sun*, 12.

21 Irvin D. Yalom, *Existential Psychotherapy* (New York: Basic Books, 1980), 44–45; idem, *Staring at the Sun: Overcoming the Terror of Death* (San Francisco: Jossey-Bass, 2008), 11.

22 Solomon, Greenberg, and Pyszczynski, *The Worm at the Core*, 12, 17–18.

conflict or a driving force toward openness and freedom.²³ Thus, on the social and political level, freedom of conscience proves to be the mechanism capable of converting this ambivalence into openness, becoming the foundation for tolerance, pluralism, and lasting peace.

2.2. Existentialist Perspectives

Existentialist philosophy provides a profound framework for understanding the relationship between the fear of death and inner freedom. Søren Kierkegaard described existential anxiety as the “dizziness of freedom,” suggesting that the human being, aware of infinite possibilities, inevitably confronts their own finitude.²⁴ Martin Heidegger developed the concept of *Sein-zum-Tode* (being-toward-death), showing that “from the moment of birth, a human is old enough to die”²⁵. For him, authenticity becomes possible only by assuming death as a constitutive part of existence.

Jean-Paul Sartre emphasized the radical freedom of the human being: “we are condemned to be free,” which entails an absolute responsibility for how we relate to our own finitude.²⁶ Viktor Frankl, from a logotherapeutic perspective, added that the meaning of life represents the supreme antidote to existential anxiety: “it does not matter what we expect from life, but rather what life expects from us”.²⁷

This tension was formulated by Paul Tillich in his famous statement: “anxiety is the existential awareness of non-being.” For Tillich, the courage to be does not mean denying death, but integrating it into the inevitable horizon of being.²⁸

2.3. The Spiritual Dimension

Henri Nouwen remarks that people are “full of fears,” and death constitutes the supreme fear, one that robs freedom and opens the way for ma-

23 Jonathan Arrowood and Cathy Cox, *Terror Management Theory and Prosocial Behavior* (New York: Academic Press, 2023), 39; Clay Routledge and Matthew Vess, *Handbook of Terror Management Theory* (San Diego: Elsevier, 2019), 5–6.

24 Kierkegaard, *The Concept of Anxiety*, 61.

25 Heidegger, *Ființă și timp*, 327, 615.

26 Jean-Paul Sartre, *Being and Nothingness*, citat în William Spade, *Jean-Paul Sartre's Being and Nothingness: Critical Essays* (New York: Routledge, 2010), 101, 117.

27 Frankl, *Man's Search for Meaning*, 85.

28 Paul Tillich, *The Courage to Be* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1952), 35.

nipulation through threats and promises.²⁹ The fear of death, therefore, is not reduced to a psychological experience but has a profound spiritual dimension.

From a theological perspective, death is described not as an absolute end but as a “sleep” or as a passage into a new reality (1 Thessalonians 4:13–18; John 11:25). Stephen Lloyd Garrett observes that the fear of disappearance is not limited to those without faith: even believers may be haunted by the doubt that the afterlife might not be real.³⁰

The problem becomes especially acute when hope in the resurrection disappears—a situation in which, according to Raoul Dederen, the fear of death remains the most fundamental fear experienced by human beings. He shows that the hope of the resurrection is the element that gives meaning to existence and diminishes anguish, directing the believer toward inner freedom.³¹

Dumitru Stăniloae emphasizes the spiritual dimension of death, stating that “death reveals to our being the mystery of personhood, the depth of existence as person, the importance of personal existence,” and, moreover, “death is the boundary at which God appears to us alive, the Creator, who alone has immortality (1 Tim. 6:16).”³²

The same perspective of hope is found in Jürgen Moltmann, for whom Christianity is not only a religion of salvation but above all a religion of active hope, “oriented and advancing toward the future, and therefore revolutionizing and transforming the present.”³³ Likewise, John Dunlop links the fear of death to the way of life lived in faith, affirming that “to die well is nothing other than to live well until the end.”³⁴

Therefore, the spiritual dimension of the fear of death shows that death is not an absolute end but a passage and an encounter: a moment of revelation of the personal mystery and of meeting God, where faith transforms fear into inner freedom through the reality of the resurrection.

29 Nouwen, *Our Greatest Gift*, 17.

30 Stephen Lloyd Garrett, *When Death Speaks* (Victoria, BC: FriesenPress, 2013), 3.

31 Dederen, *Handbook of Seventh-Day Adventist Theology*, 330.

32 Dumitru Stăniloae, *Teologia Dogmatică Ortodoxă*, vol. 3 (București: Institutul Biblic și de Misiune al Bisericii Ortodoxe Române, 1997), 145, 146.

33 Jürgen Moltmann, *Theology of Hope* (San Francisco: Harper, 1967), 16.

34 John Dunlop, *Finishing Well to the Glory of God* (Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2011), 8.

2.4. *Toward Inner Freedom*

The integration of these perspectives leads to the conclusion that the fear of death cannot be overcome through mere rationalization or denial. It is transformed when the individual embraces inner freedom through the discovery of meaning (Frankl), authentic confrontation (Heidegger), eschatological hope (theology), and trust in a benevolent God (the psychology of religion). Freedom of conscience thus becomes the space in which a person decides whether death will be experienced as a paralyzing threat or as an opportunity to affirm dignity and faith. This inner liberation becomes exemplarily visible in martyrdom, where freedom of conscience is borne witness to until the very end. In this sense, freedom of conscience functions as an existential shield against the instrumentalization of fear in the public sphere.

3. Martyrdom as an Expression of Freedom of Conscience

3.1. *Martyrdom – Between Fear, Suffering, and Freedom*

Throughout history, martyrdom has represented the supreme expression of freedom of conscience. Costică Brădăţan draws attention to the dangerous fidelity to one's own convictions: "If you decide to remain faithful to your opinions, you will no longer be! Your own death will be your last chance to put your ideas into practice. On the other hand, if you choose to 'betray' your ideas (and perhaps also yourself), you remain alive, but without convictions to live by"³⁵.

In the case of Christians, the martyr does not die for an idea, but for a personal and divine relationship. "The martyr accepts this price with humility, even with joy, considering it an honor to walk in the footsteps of his Savior"³⁶. Christian martyrdom transcends earthly existence and projects the martyr into eternity, as recorded by the apostle John: "Do not fear what you are about to suffer. Behold, the devil is about to throw some of you into prison, that you may be tested, and for ten days you will have tribulation. Be faithful unto death, and I will give you the crown of life" (Revelation 2:10).

35 Brădăţan, "Philosophy as an Art of Dying."

36 Emanuel Adrian Sârbu, *Suicidul. O analiză teologică* (Bucureşti: Editura Ars Academica, 2011), 257.

Christianity has, over time, developed a profound understanding of the role of suffering, not only as theological explanation but as an existential experience with transformative value. The apostle Paul affirms: “More than that, we rejoice in our sufferings, knowing that suffering produces endurance, and endurance produces character, and character produces hope” (Romans 5:3–4). Thus, pain can become a factor of spiritual growth, cultivating patience, hope, and trust in God.

Contemporary theological debates have raised a fundamental question: can God experience suffering? While traditional theology connected divine immutability with the absence of any sensitivity, theologians such as Paul S. Fiddes argue the opposite. In his view, divine love implies participation in human suffering and, through this, openness to change: “Love must mean suffering, (...) suffering must mean change and being changed. To love is to be in a relationship in which what the beloved does modifies one’s own experience. The beloved changes our life”³⁷.

Thus, painful experience occupies a central place in the plan of salvation, because it connects human beings with God in a relationship capable of transforming suffering into an opportunity for faith and hope. In an eschatological horizon, Samuele Bacchiocchi reminds us that the end of suffering is guaranteed through the return of Christ, who “will put an end to human perversity and suffering and will restore peace, justice, and prosperity on this earth”³⁸. This promise offers the believer meaning and purpose in the midst of suffering, orienting him toward final healing and complete restoration in communion with God.

Therefore, martyrdom is not only a theological or historical theme, but also a living expression of freedom of conscience, with direct impact on the foundation of human rights (especially religious freedom), on community education (models of fidelity and dignity), and on the construction of lasting peace, because it shows that there are values higher than violence and biological survival.

3.2. Martiriul în psihologie și filosofie

From a psychological perspective, Terror Management Theory (TMT) shows that once individuals become aware of their own mortality, they

37 Fiddes, *The Creative Suffering of God*, 50.

38 Samuele Bacchiocchi, *The Advent Hope for Human Hopelessness* (Berrien Springs, MI: Biblical Perspectives, 2001), 184.

seek refuge in cultural and religious worldviews, in self-esteem, and in close relationships, all of which serve to reduce anxiety and provide a meaningful framework for existence.³⁹ The sacrifice of the martyr can thus be understood as a profound response to the fear of death: he integrates his own disappearance into a vision that transcends mere biological survival and gives communal meaning to the experience of the limit. Freedom of conscience is manifested here as the inner force to choose fidelity to the very end, even when the biological instinct for self-preservation would dictate the opposite.

On the philosophical level, Costică Brădăţan asserts that death becomes “the skillful editor who arranges your life so that it appears intelligible”⁴⁰. The martyr is, in this sense, the figure who demonstrates that there are realities higher than biological survival. Moreover, “the death of martyrs is beneficial for others”⁴¹, as David Seeley noted, a reality evident in Christian history, where the blood of the martyrs became “the seed of new life”⁴². In this sense, the martyr’s death is not suicide but a lesson in dignity and inner freedom, an educational act that becomes an example for the community. Thus, martyrdom takes shape as a pedagogy of freedom of conscience, showing future generations that authenticity and fidelity cannot be compromised without losing the very essence of humanity.

This intuition—that freedom of conscience is verified at the limit—will be further developed philosophically in the following section, through the tradition of philosophical martyrs.

3.3. *The Narrative Dimension of Martyrdom*

From the perspective of Christian narrative therapy, martyrdom can be understood as the rewriting of a personal history within the framework of

39 Lindsey A. Harvell și Gwendolyn S. Nisbett, ed., *Denying Death: An Interdisciplinary Approach to Terror Management Theory* (New York: Routledge, 2016), 137; Robert B. Arrowood și Cathy R. Cox, *Terror Management Theory: A Practical Review of Research and Application* (Leiden: Brill, 2023), 39.

40 Brădăţan, *Dying for Ideas*, 7.

41 David Seeley, *The Noble Death: Graeco-Roman Martyrology and Paul’s Concept of Salvation*, Journal for the Study of the New Testament Supplement Series 28 (Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1990), 92.

42 Tertullian, *The Apology for the Christians*, trad. T. Herbert Bindley (Oxford: Parker and Co., 1890), 147.

the divine narrative. As the literature on narrative psychology emphasizes, life consists of meaningful stories, and the therapeutic process helps clients reinterpret and restructure these stories in order to discover new perspectives and solutions that support well-being.⁴³

A central element is externalization and narrative rewriting: the person no longer confuses the problem with their identity but integrates it into a broader framework of meaning. The therapeutic narrative restructures personal experiences in line with preferred realities and offers a new perspective on life.⁴⁴ This reframing aligns with the Christian faith, where the Gospel itself is “a story—about the birth, ministry, death, and resurrection of Christ.”⁴⁵

Thus, the life of the martyr, with its sufferings and death, is integrated into a greater narrative—the narrative of the cross and resurrection—transforming fear into hope. “The Christian’s life narrative, being integrated into the narrative of the life, death, and resurrection of Jesus Christ, can transform the anxiety of death into an experience of liberation and hope.”⁴⁶

In this way, martyrdom is not reduced to the individual dimension but becomes a narrative pedagogy of freedom of conscience, through which the community receives a living lesson in authenticity, dignity, and fidelity that underpins education and lasting peace. The narrative dimension has explicit formative consequences; section 5.1 will show how it becomes an educational framework for freedom of conscience.

4. Contemporary Philosophical Reflections – Death Chosen for Truth as the Supreme Act of Authenticity

Contemporary philosophy has reopened the theme of death not only as an ontological problem but also as a decisive test of human authenticity. Costică Brădățașan’s contribution is remarkable: in “Dying for Ideas” (2015), he shows that death assumed for the sake of truth constitutes the radical expression of freedom of conscience. Unlike inevitable biological death,

43 B. G. Çakmak, “Spirituality in Narrative Therapy: A Review Study,” *Spiritual Psychology and Counseling* 7, no. 3 (2022): 316–336. (p.320)

44 Ispas, “Christian Narrative Therapy,” 125.

45 R. Galvin, *Narrative Therapy in Pastoral Ministry*, n.d., <http://justsolutions.eu/Resources/NarrTherGalvin.pdf>, 80.

46 Ispas, “Christian Narrative Therapy,” 125.

martyrdom is a deliberate choice: the individual renounces life in order to remain faithful to an idea, a belief, or a principle. In this choice, fear is not denied but transformed into existential courage.

4.1. *Brădăţan and the Tradition of Philosophical Martyrs*

Brădăţan retrieves the figure of the philosophical martyr, from Socrates—who preferred death over intellectual compromise—to Giordano Bruno, burned at the stake for his fidelity to cosmological truths. In these lives, death does not appear as a tragic accident but as an act of ontological testimony: existence becomes authentic at the very moment when the individual chooses to die for what he considers essential. “Philosophical death,” says Brădăţan, is a form of thought lived to the end: philosophy ceases to be mere discourse and becomes life, since its value is not confirmed by arguments but by the willingness to die for them.⁴⁷ In this sense, the philosophical martyr transforms death into a pedagogical work: it becomes a message for the community and for future generations.

This intuition resonates with Michel de Montaigne’s statement in *Essays*: “to philosophize is to learn to die.”⁴⁸ Kierkegaard deepened it, describing existential anxiety as the “dizziness of freedom,” the inevitable confrontation with finitude.⁴⁹ Heidegger radicalized it through his famous idea of being-toward-death, emphasizing that man is “old enough to die” from the very moment of birth.⁵⁰ Sartre, in turn, showed that “man is condemned to be free,” with no external excuse that can absolve him of responsibility for his choices—even in the face of death.⁵¹

In parallel, Viktor Frankl emphasized that man can preserve his freedom even in conditions of extreme suffering, finding meaning in tragedy. For him, man’s supreme freedom lies in the power to choose his attitude toward his own death.⁵² Irvin Yalom argued that the authenticity of life is inseparable from the confrontation with death⁵³, while Ernest Becker demonstrated that all civilization is built upon the denial of this confron-

47 Brădăţan, *Dying for Ideas*, 6–7.

48 Michel de Montaigne, *The Complete Essays*, ed. and trans. M. A. Screech (London: Penguin Books, 1993), 128

49 Kierkegaard, *The Concept of Anxiety*, 61.

50 Heidegger, *Fiinţă şi timp*, 327.

51 Spade, *Jean-Paul Sartre’s Being and Nothingness: Class Lecture Notes*, 101, 117.

52 Frankl, *Man’s Search for Meaning*, 85.

53 Yalom, *Psihoterapia existenţială*, 45.

tation.⁵⁴ By contrast, precisely because most cultures avoid death, those figures who confront it—philosophical martyrs—become educators of authenticity and freedom.

Thus, Brădățan stands within a broad tradition that begins with classical philosophical martyrdom and extends to contemporary existentialist and psychological reflections, placing at the center of human thought the relationship with death as the supreme test of authenticity.

4.2. Authenticity, Dignity, and Civic Consequences: Human Rights and Peace

Brădățan shows that death chosen for truth is not a capitulation but an affirmation of dignity: when the individual refuses to live under the constraint of compromise, his act becomes creative—it generates meaning, example, and horizons of freedom for others. The martyr (whether philosophical or religious) becomes proof that there are values transcending biological survival, and that freedom of conscience cannot be annulled by any external force.⁵⁵

On the civic level, this authenticity has normative force: if freedom of conscience grounds dignity, then the martyr is the supreme pedagogue of freedom. His sacrifice demonstrates that no political order and no form of oppression can defeat a liberated conscience. Man transcends the fear of death by engaging in causes that provide meaning and freedom.⁵⁶ In Levinas's words, death is an "absolutely certain possibility"⁵⁷, a concept taken from Heidegger but transformed by him into a source of radical ethical responsibility toward the other. In this sense, the martyr acquires normative relevance.

In a world saturated with fear, manipulation, and conformity, the example of martyrs shows that peace is not achieved through submission but through fidelity to values. Brădățan states bluntly: "if you choose to 'betray' your ideas (and perhaps also yourself), you remain alive, but without convictions by which to live"⁵⁸. Hence emerges a convergence

54 Solomon, Greenberg, and Pyszczynski, *The Worm at the Core*, 6.

55 Brădățan, "Philosophy as an Art of Dying."

56 Becker, *The Denial of Death*, 150.

57 Emmanuel Lévinas, *God, Death, and Time* (Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press, 2000), 49.

58 Brădățan, "Philosophy as an Art of Dying."

with theology and existential psychology: authenticity and lasting peace appear only where freedom of conscience overcomes the fear of death and becomes the foundation for both human rights and social cohesion.

5. Educational Implications and Durable Peace

5.1. *Freedom of Conscience as the Foundation of Authentic Education*

Freedom of conscience is not manifested only in extreme situations such as martyrdom but also constitutes the foundation of any authentic education. Practical theology emphasizes that the church's reflection and action must be related to the real life of believers and to their concrete needs.⁵⁹

In this sense, education for freedom of conscience means cultivating the capacity to think critically, to discern spiritually, and to live in truth—even in a social climate marked by conformity and fear. Schleiermacher and Anderson emphasized that theology becomes relevant only when it touches everyday life, where people face pain, anxiety, and moral pressures.⁶⁰

This vision is complemented by the perspective of narrative psychology, which shows that people form their identity through stories.⁶¹ To educate for freedom of conscience therefore means creating the framework in which each person can rewrite their own life narrative in relation to ethical and spiritual values, rather than fears or external constraints.

In this process, faith becomes a space of rewriting and re-signification of existence, where existential anxiety is integrated and transformed into resilience, meaning, and hope, nurturing a civic culture of responsibility and lasting peace.

5.2. *Fear of Death and Education for Human Rights*

Death and the fear of death represent nerve centers of human existence, and the way in which they are integrated influences social and political behavior. Terror Management Theory (TMT) shows that fear of death

59 Friedrich Schleiermacher, *Brief Outline of Theology as a Field of Study*, trans. Terrence N. Tice (Lewiston, NY: Edwin Mellen Press, 2000), 15.

60 Schleiermacher, *Brief Outline of Theology as a Field of Study*, 15.; Ray S. Anderson, *The Shape of Practical Theology: Empowering Ministry through Theological Praxis* (Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 2001), 22.

61 Charles V. Gerkin, *The Living Human Document: Re-Visioning Pastoral Counseling in a Hermeneutical Mode* (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1984), 37.

can fuel intolerance, ideological rigidity, and violence when politically exploited; yet when consciously confronted and spiritually transformed, the same fear becomes a source of compassion, solidarity, and openness.⁶²

In contemporary civic education, fear is often instrumentalized in populist and totalitarian discourses to limit the inner autonomy of citizens. A civic literacy of the mechanisms of fear, inspired by TMT, reduces susceptibility to “threat–salvation” rhetoric and strengthens democratic discernment. Education for freedom of conscience supports the architecture of human rights: it protects moral autonomy, pluralism of beliefs, and dignity—the very benchmarks that instrumentalized fear tends to undermine.⁶³

Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru argues that religious freedom is a natural right of the person and a pillar of democratic order, which obliges the state to guarantee a legal framework for the protection of conscience against any form of coercion.⁶⁴ In a pluralist society, the integration of death into a broader narrative—whether religious or humanist—diminishes existential anxiety and cultivates respect for the diversity of beliefs. In this sense, the civic literacy of fear becomes an essential component of education for human rights: it translates into the curriculum what the theology of hope and existential psychology describe as inner liberation.

5.3. Freedom of Conscience and Lasting Peace

A lasting peace cannot be built solely on political treaties; it also requires the recognition of each person’s inner freedom as the foundation of authentic coexistence. Recasting Tillich’s thesis in a social key, the courage to be is born when the anxiety of non-existence is transformed into the affirmation of meaning.⁶⁵

A community made up of individuals free in their conscience, capable of facing the fear of death with hope and meaning, is less prone to hatred and violence. This perspective is also empirically confirmed: the

62 Ispas, “Terror Management Theory and Fear of Death”.

63 Nouwen, *Our Greatest Gift*, 17.

64 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, “Religious Liberty – A Natural Human Right,” *Jurnalul Libertății de Conștiință* 2, no. 1 (2015): 595-608. <https://www.jurnal.constiintasiliberate.ro/index.php/freedom/article/view/47>.

65 Tillich, *The Courage to Be*, 35.

literature on the image of God shows that the perception of a benevolent divinity is associated with decreased anxiety and increased prosocial behaviors. By contrast, authoritarian or punitive representations tend to fuel conflict and suspicion.⁶⁶ Convergent experimental studies demonstrate that the mere activation of the concept of God increases generosity toward strangers, and that beliefs in a morally concerned divinity foster cooperation in large groups, reducing social suspicion.⁶⁷ It follows that freedom of conscience has direct consequences for social peace: beliefs that free human beings from fear strengthen democracy and community cohesion.

In conclusion, peace cannot exist without freedom of conscience. The one who overcomes the fundamental fear of existence can live in truth and contribute to a just and reconciled society. Only the person free before death can truly be a builder of peace.

6. Conclusion

Freedom of conscience proves to be more than a legal concept or a fundamental right inscribed in international treaties: it is the very essence of human dignity and the framework within which the fear of death, existential anxiety, and eschatological hope are confronted. Lasting peace cannot be built without freedom of conscience, and martyrdom constitutes its canonical proof. The present analysis has shown that, in the Christian tradition, inner freedom is tested most clearly in times of crisis—and martyrdom remains the supreme expression of fidelity to the truth.

On a psychological level, Terror Management Theory (TMT) confirms that the fear of death is a deep mechanism shaping social and political behavior. It can generate intolerance, rigidity, and aggression when exploited, but it can also foster compassion and solidarity when consciously confronted. Complementarily, research on the image of God shows that theological perceptions directly influence the level of existential anxiety: a benevolent and protective God sustains spiritual resilience, whereas

66 Kathryn A. Johnson and Adam B. Cohen, "Authoritarian and Benevolent God Representations and the Two Sides of Prosociality," *Behavioral and Brain Sciences* 39 (January 2016): e16, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X15000461>.

67 Ara Norenzayan and Azim F. Shariff, "The Origin and Evolution of Religious Prosociality," *Science* 322, no. 5898 (2008): 58–62, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1158757>.

a distant or authoritarian God amplifies fear. This demonstrates that freedom of conscience, understood as the free choice of one's relation to the divine, has profound implications for mental health and social peace.

From an existentialist perspective, Kierkegaard, Heidegger, and Sartre showed that the acceptance of one's own mortality is the key to authenticity. Frankl complemented this view through his logotherapy, demonstrating that the meaning of life can transform even suffering and death into a victory of the spirit. Paul Tillich named this process "the courage to be," that is, the transformation of the anxiety of non-being into the affirmation of meaning.

These ideas are taken up and further developed by Brădățan, who argues that death chosen for the sake of truth is the supreme act of authenticity: the martyr shows the world that there are values higher than biological survival and that freedom of conscience cannot be annulled by coercion.

On the educational and social level, practical theology and narrative therapy provide a framework for cultivating freedom of conscience in everyday life. Authentic education does not merely form competences but helps individuals to rewrite their identity narratives in relation to values of truth, hope, and dignity. At the same time, the memory of martyrs functions as a transgenerational educational model, offering societies moral and civic landmarks for building peace.

Thus, from the intersection of psychology, theology, and philosophy, a clear thesis emerges: genuine peace cannot be conceived without freedom of conscience. The person who lives under the domination of the fear of death becomes vulnerable to manipulation, intolerance, and violence. By contrast, the human being who confronts this fear through faith, meaning, and authenticity is able to live in truth and to build social relationships based on respect and reconciliation.

Freedom of conscience, tested in the face of death, thus becomes the foundation of authentic education and of a peaceful social order. In Brădățan's conception, death embraced for the sake of truth is not a failure, but a victory of the spirit over biological fragility. In theological logic, it becomes an echo of eschatological hope: the love that overcomes fear and the life that rises out of death.

In conclusion, only the person free in conscience, able to face death without renouncing truth, can be a builder of peace. Freedom of conscience, martyrdom, and existential courage converge at this point: true

human dignity is revealed when the person chooses to live and, if necessary, to die for what is eternal.

Bibliography:

- ✦ ANDERSON, Ray S. *The Shape of Practical Theology: Empowering Ministry through Theological Praxis*. Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 2001.
- ✦ ARROWOOD, Jonathan, and Cathy Cox. *Terror Management Theory and Prosocial Behavior*. New York: Academic Press, 2023.
- ✦ BACCHIOCCHI, Samuele. *The Advent Hope for Human Hopelessness*. Berrien Springs, MI: Biblical Perspectives, 2001.
- ✦ BECKER, Ernest. *The Denial of Death*. New York: Free Press, 1973.
- ✦ BRĂDĂȚAN, Costică. *Dying for Ideas: The Dangerous Lives of the Philosophers*. London: Bloomsbury UK, 2015.
- ✦ BRĂDĂȚAN, Costică. "Philosophy as an Art of Dying." *The New York Times Opinionator*, June 12, 2011. <https://archive.nytimes.com/opinionator.blogs.nytimes.com/2011/06/12/philosophy-as-an-art-of-dying/>.
- ✦ ÇAKMAK, B. G. "Spirituality in Narrative Therapy: A Review Study." *Spiritual Psychology and Counseling* 7, no. 3 (2022): 316–336.
- ✦ DEDEREN, Raoul. *Handbook of Seventh-Day Adventist Theology*. Vol. 12, Commentary Reference Series. Hagerstown, MD: Review and Herald Publishing Association, 2001.
- ✦ DUNLOP, John. *Finishing Well to the Glory of God*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2011.
- ✦ FIDDES, Paul S. *The Creative Suffering of God*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1992.
- ✦ FOLKENBERG, Robert S. *Called in Christ*. Nampa, ID: Pacific Press® Publishing Association, 2013.
- ✦ FRANKL, Viktor E. *Man's Search for Meaning: An Introduction to Logotherapy*. Boston: Beacon Press, 1992.
- ✦ GALVIN, R. *Narrative Therapy in Pastoral Ministry*. n.d. <http://justsolutions.eu/Resources/NarrTherGalvin.pdf>.
- ✦ GARRET, Stephen Lloyd. *When Death Speaks*. Victoria, BC: Friesen-Press, 2013.

- ✦ GERKIN, Charles V. *The Living Human Document: Re-Visioning Pastoral Counseling in a Hermeneutical Mode*. Nashville: Abingdon Press, 1984.
- ✦ HEIDEGGER, Martin. *Ființă și timp*. Trad. Gabriel Liiceanu și Cătălin Cioabă. București: Humanitas, 2003.
- ✦ ISPAS, Narcisa. "Christian Narrative Therapy: Reconstructing Identity and Spiritual Healing Through Story." *RAIS Journal for Social Sciences* 9, no. 1 (2025): 119–137. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15428078>.
- ✦ ISPAS, Narcisa. "Existential Perspectives on the Fear of Death." *RAIS Conference Proceedings*, April 17–18, 2025: 183–190. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15474925>.
- ✦ ISPAS, Narcisa. "Terror Management Theory and Fear of Death." *Scientia Moralitas Conference Proceedings*, February 20–21, 2025: 104–112. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15075876>.
- ✦ JOHNSON, Kathryn A., and Adam B. COHEN. "Authoritarian and Benevolent God Representations and the Two Sides of Prosociality." *Behavioral and Brain Sciences* 39 (January 2016): e16. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X15000461>.
- ✦ KASTENBAUM, Robert. *The Psychology of Death*. 3rd ed. New York: Springer Publishing Company, 2000.
- ✦ KIERKEGAARD, Søren. *The Concept of Anxiety: A Simple Psychological-y Orienting Deliberation on the Dogmatic Issue of Hereditary Sin*. Edited and translated by Reidar Thomte, in collaboration with Albert B. Anderson. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1980.
- ✦ LEVINAS, Emmanuel. *God, Death, and Time*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press, 2000.
- ✦ MOLTSMANN, Jürgen. *Theology of Hope*. San Francisco: Harper, 1967.
- ✦ MONTAIGNE, Michel de. *The Complete Essays*. Edited and translated by M. A. Screech. London: Penguin Books, 1993.
- ✦ NIEBUHR, H. Richard. "The Story of Our Life." In *Why Narrative? Readings in Narrative Theology*, edited by Stanley Hauerwas and L. Gregory Jones, 21–44. Eugene, OR: Wipf and Stock, 1997.
- ✦ NORENZAYAN, Ara, and Azim F. Shariff. "The Origin and Evolution of Religious Prosociality." *Science* 322, no. 5898 (2008): 58–62. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1158757>.
- ✦ NOWEN, Henri J. M. *Our Greatest Gift: A Meditation on Dying and Caring*. San Francisco: HarperSanFrancisco, 1995.

- ✦ ROTARU, Ioan-Gheorghe. "Religious Liberty – A Natural Human Right." *Jurnalul Libertății de Conștiință* 2, no. 1 (2015): 595-608. <https://www.jurnal.constiintasilibertate.ro/index.php/freedom/article/view/47>.
- ✦ ROUTLEDGE, Clay, and Matthew Vess. *Handbook of Terror Management Theory*. San Diego: Elsevier, 2019.
- ✦ SÂRBU, Emanuel Adrian. *Suicidul. O analiză teologică*. București: Editura Ars Academica, 2011.
- ✦ SCHLEIERMACHER, Friedrich. *Brief Outline of Theology as a Field of Study*. Translated by Terrence N. Tice. Schleiermacher Studies and Translations, vol. 1. Lewiston, NY: Edwin Mellen Press, 2000. (Original work published 1811, 1830).
- ✦ SEELEY, David. *The Noble Death: Graeco-Roman Martyrology and Paul's Concept of Salvation*. Journal for the Study of the New Testament Supplement Series 28. Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1990.
- ✦ SOLOMON, Sheldon; GREENBERG, Jeff; and PYSZCZYNSKI, Tom. *The Worm at the Core: On the Role of Death in Life*. New York: Random House, 2015.
- ✦ SPADE, Paul Vincent. *Jean-Paul Sartre's Being and Nothingness: Class Lecture Notes, Spring 2010*. Licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, 2010.
- ✦ STĂNILOAE, Dumitru. *Teologia Dogmatică Ortodoxă*. Vol. 3. 2nd ed. București: Editura Institutului Biblic și de Misiune al Bisericii Ortodoxe Române, 1997.
- ✦ TILLICH, Paul. *The Courage to Be*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 1952.
- ✦ TERTULLIAN. *The Apology for the Christians*. Translated by T. Herbert Bindley. Oxford: Parker and Co., 1890.
- ✦ Uniunea Europeană. *Carta Drepturilor Fundamentale a Uniunii Europene*. Art. 10. Adoptată la Nisa, 7 decembrie 2000, actualizată 2012. Accesat 18 septembrie 2025. <https://fra.europa.eu/ro/eu-charter/article/10-libertatea-de-gandire-de-constiinta-si-de-religie>.
- ✦ United Nations. *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*. 1948. <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>.
- ✦ YALOM, Irvin D. *Psihoterapia existențială*. Traducere de Bogdan Boghițoi. București: Editura Trei, 2010.
- ✦ YALOM, Irvin D. *Staring at the Sun: Overcoming the Terror of Death*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass, 2008.